

Article reference document

This document summarizes the bibliographic details of the article and includes a screenshot of the first page as visual support.

Journal	Toxins
ISSN	2072-6651
Volume	18
Issue	3
Article number	140
DOI	10.3390/toxins18030140
Published	13 March 2026

Suggested reference

Hidalgo, C., Ruiz-Moyano, S., Rodríguez, A., Córdoba, M. G., López-Corrales, M., & Serradilla, M. J. (2026). *Effects of Preharvest Application of Oxalic Acid, γ -Aminobutyric Acid, and Melatonin on the Microbiological and Physicochemical Quality of Dried Figs at Commercial Harvest and During Storage*. *Toxins*, 18(3), 140. <https://doi.org/10.3390/toxins18030140>

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Article

Effects of Preharvest Application of Oxalic Acid, γ -Aminobutyric Acid, and Melatonin on the Microbiological and Physicochemical Quality of Dried Figs at Commercial Harvest and During Storage

Cristina Hidalgo ^{1,2}, Santiago Ruiz-Moyano ^{1,2}, Alicia Rodríguez ^{1,2,*}, María G. Córdoba ^{1,2}, Margarita López-Corrales ³ and Manuel J. Serradilla ⁴

¹ Nutrición y Bromatología, Escuela de Ingenierías Agrarias, Universidad de Extremadura, 06007 Badajoz, Spain
² Instituto Universitario de Investigación en Recursos Agrarios (INURA), Avd. de la Investigación, Universidad de Extremadura, 06006 Badajoz, Spain
³ Junta de Extremadura, Centro de Investigación Fitoc. La Orden-Vadolesequera (CICYTEX), Fruticultura, Autovía Madrid-Lisboa, s/n, 06187 Gaudájar, Spain
⁴ Área de Postosecha, Valorización Vegetal y Nuevas Tecnologías, Centro de Investigaciones Científicas y Tecnológicas de Extremadura (CICYTEX), Instituto Tecnológico Agrario de Extremadura (INTELEX), Junta de Extremadura, Avda. Adolfo Suárez, s/n, 06007 Badajoz, Spain
* Correspondence: alicia@iurua.es; Tel.: +34-924492920

Abstract

The objective of this study was to evaluate the preharvest application of γ -aminobutyric acid (GABA), melatonin (MT), and oxalic acid (OA), at different concentrations and application frequencies, on the physicochemical and microbiological quality of dried figs (cv. Calabacita) at commercial harvest and after 3 and 6 months of refrigerated storage. A further aim was to determine their impact on fungal populations and mycotoxin production. The results showed that untreated dried figs had a higher frequency of *Aspergillus velutinus*, *A. tubingensis*, and *Aspergillus* section *Flavi*, whereas elicitor-treated figs exhibited a lower incidence of toxigenic fungi. *A. niger* was the main ochratoxin A (OTA)-associated species detected, although the proportion of OTA-positive figs was lower in elicitor-treated samples than in the control. Aflatoxins (AFs) were detected only sporadically in 2 mM OA treatments, consistent with the limited activity of *A. flavus* at low storage temperatures. Conversely, *Penicillium* spp. were widespread but were associated with citrinin (CIT) production only under 2 mM OA treatments. Among the *Alternaria* toxins, alternariol (ALT) was detected solely in dried figs treated with 1 mM OA. Notably, all investigated mycotoxins were below the limit of detection (LOD) in dried figs treated with 0.5 mM MT. Moderate elicitor concentrations (e.g., 0.5 mM MT and 50 mM GABA) and multiple preharvest applications generally provided the best balance between fungal suppression and fruit quality, significantly reducing *Aspergillus* spp. occurrence without promoting the growth of undesirable species. Overall, elicitor treatments decreased the incidence of toxigenic fungi, most likely through direct antifungal effects in senescent dried fruit rather than by inducing host defences. The combined use of preharvest elicitors with appropriate drying and storage conditions is a promising strategy to control fungal contamination and mycotoxin accumulation in dried figs while maintaining quality from preharvest storage. Further research is needed to optimise elicitor concentrations and application timing.

Keywords: elicitors; preharvest treatment; dried figs; physicochemical quality; fungal populations; mycotoxins; storage

Received: 7 February 2026
Revised: 6 March 2026
Accepted: 7 March 2026
Published: 13 March 2026

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Toxins 2026, 18, 140 <https://doi.org/10.3390/toxins18030140>

Figure 1. Screenshot of the first page of the original article.